

The Effect of Students' Emotional Intelligence Approach in Increasing the Effectiveness of Arabic Learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract:- This study examines the emotional intelligence approach that is applied to learning Arabic in Indonesia. This research uses descriptive research, namely research based on literature review which is described through descriptions using library sources such as books, journals and laws, and regulations related to the research topic. In this study, it is explained that the use of an emotional intelligence approach in learning Arabic has great benefits on the learning development of students. The current pandemic situation forces all people to think harder and creatively in facing the challenges that exist, including in the realm of education. The online system is an online distance learning system implemented during this pandemic. There are many obstacles faced by teachers and students in the learning process, such as the difficulty of understanding the material to increase student stress levels. Therefore, an emotional intelligence approach is needed in this learning process so that students can motivate themselves, be able to control themselves to be responsible for their duties as students.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, learning, Arabic.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Language is one of the important things in the continuity of human life. Language is used as a communication tool that can translate thoughts and feelings experienced. Another definition of language is a collection of pronunciations used by community groups in expressing their goals, thoughts, and feelings. The use of language cannot be separated from every activity carried out by humans, namely as a means of communication. In addition, language is also used in expressing feelings, a tool for thinking, and language supports all knowledge possessed by humans (Alfaini, 2021).

One of the languages recognized by the whole world because it has different features and characteristics from other languages is Arabic. This is because Arabic is recognized as having superior literary content to be understood and studied. In addition, Arabic is destined to become the language in the Qur'an with the aim of conveying the word of Allah, namely all His commands and prohibitions to His creatures. Arabic is also an international language with the largest number of speakers in the world, which is around 200,000,000 speakers and is used by 20 countries in the world. The recognition of Arabic as an international language makes Arabic one of the special subjects taught by several schools in Indonesia. Arabic language learning in Indonesia already exists at all levels of education, such as Elementary School (SD) or Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (MI) to university level (Tianhuri, 2021).

Various points of view and ways of thinking arise regarding the assessment of Arabic learning. Some see Arabic as a religious language. This happens because Arabic is considered a tool for understanding and translating texts that use Arabic. There are also those who view that learning Arabic is learning about Islamic religious knowledge. Regardless of how people judge what and how to learn Arabic, if you look more closely you will find that learning Arabic has many problems and obstacles. One of them is that Arabic teaching and learning activities cannot be carried out face-to-face due to the Covid-19 pandemic. This phenomenon requires learning institutions to apply online learning (in the network) to overcome it. The online learning that has been done is in fact not without problems (Kosim et al., 2018).

Various obstacles and obstacles faced by teachers in implementing programmed online programs. Therefore, it is necessary for innovations to be carried out to solve problems that arise in order to make a positive contribution in the field of learning Arabic in an effort to answer the challenges of today's learning, high effort, and creativity are needed to foster student interest in learning Arabic (Hidayat, 2020).). In the modern era like today, an educator, namely a teacher, must be smart and careful in collaborating strategies, media, methods, and learning models that are used according to the needs and characteristics of their students. Arabic subject teachers need to fade the difficult and foreign stigma attached to learning Arabic so that emotionally there will be a concentration of attention on the challenges they face (Riqza & Muassomah, 2020).

This can be done and overcome through the emotional intelligence approach of students. The goal is to provide self-motivation, control empathy, and impulses such as moods in order to improve students' thinking skills. This emotional aspect of human development needs to be maintained so that it does not become a disturbance in other aspects of life (Muradi, 2013). Parents and teachers really need to know the development of emotional intelligence possessed by children or students as a basic need for information about child development. In addition, the importance of this understanding is intended so that parents and teachers can determine the right steps in dealing with various problems and challenges related to child development (Ratnaningtyas, 2019).

Based on this background the author will conduct research on the Effect of the Emotional Intelligence Approach of Students in Improving the Effectiveness of Arabic Learning in the Covid-19 Pandemic Period. Then emotional approach referred to in this study is the method or

method used to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the learning process by collaborating aspects of emotional intelligence in it. The aim is to stimulate a positive relationship between teachers and students in the learning process carried out.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a literature review research design, namely research that examines and criticizes scientific knowledge, ideas, and findings that have an academic orientation. In addition, this research will be able to contribute theoretically and methodologically to a chosen topic. The analysis used in this research is descriptive, namely describing and analyzing the problems and solutions that can be given at this time. The approach chosen is qualitative, in other words, this research is a qualitative descriptive study. This study aims to obtain data on the issues that have occurred. This study will describe and explain how the emotional intelligence approach is applied in students' online learning of Arabic.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Learning Arabic and Its Problems in the Pandemic Era

Learning is an effort made by a person consciously with the aim of positive behavior changes according to his condition. In addition, learning is also defined as an activity carried out to guide students. In other words, learning is a process that is systematically arranged with supporting elements or facilities, equipment as well as systematic steps to achieve learning objectives so that students can form spiritual, active, and more skilled morals. This can occur due to social interaction during the teaching and learning process and the experience gained. Arabic is a scientific discipline that consists of all aspects of language and the elements contained in it. Broadly speaking, it is stated that Arabic language skills have similarities with other language skills (Tajuddin, 2017).

The first element is listening skills, the first step that must be learned in a foreign language is paying attention. The second element is speaking skills, namely skills related to spoken language. Furthermore, the third element is reading skills, namely skills related to the ability to understand someone about written texts. This third element has a significant difference between the first and second elements, namely listening and speaking. This is because the conversion process does not only use the mouth as a place to talk but there are several other factors that affect a person's understanding such as gestures. The last and fourth element is writing skills. In this writing skill, all the previous elements must be present and mastered. Aspects that must be mastered are generalist or vocabulary, grammar, literature to determine the appropriate dictionary. This is because writing is an activity that is needed to provide understanding to others (Qudrotulloh et al., 2021).

Learning Arabic certainly experiences various problems in the process. The problems that occur can be divided into two dimensions, namely problems that occur in the student dimension and the teacher dimension. In the student dimension, the problems that arise are related to the skills

possessed by students, interests, learning motivation, learning attitudes, the level of concentration of students in receiving information and knowledge (Mukrandi, 2020). While the problems that arise from the teacher dimension are problems that arise before, during the learning process, and when evaluating learning. The problems that often occur are related to learning resources and teaching materials that will be used. Based on the dominant factors in influencing the occurrence of learning problems, it can be divided into two factors, namely internal factors and external factors which are shown in table 1 as follows.

Factor's Affecting	Explanation
Internal Factor	Intelligence: the basic ability that students have to accept learning.
	Attention: the activity that students have to focus on something. Good attention to students will greatly affect good learning outcomes.
	Interests: With the appropriate interest will affect the seriousness of student learning.
	Talent: potential skills possessed by students.
	Motivation: The basic drive that gives a person direction to achieve his goals.
	Readiness: the readiness of students will affect the level of knowledge transfer from teachers to students.
Eksternal Factor	Family: at this level, students will be taught basic things such as beliefs, cultural values, morals, and skills. Families really have a big influence on student learning outcomes. Some things that have a big influence such as the atmosphere of the house and the economic level of the family.
	Schools: Some things that have an influence related to this school are teaching methods, the relationship between teachers and students, the level of discipline possessed by the school, facilities, and infrastructure to learning media that provide opportunities for students to get more learning experiences.
	Society: Some of the things that have an influence on student learning related to this community are the form of community life to the influence of friends who hang out in the community.

Table 1: Dominant Factors Affecting Student Learning

Source: (Mukrandi, 2020)

B. Overview of Learning Arabic using Students' Emotional Intelligence Approach

Learning is a combination consisting of human elements, facilities, equipment, and methods used to achieve learning objectives. In addition, learning is also defined as a process carried out between students and the environment so that there is a change in behavior for the better due to external and internal factors. While language is a tool used to communicate in everyday life so that language appears in the community. This is what causes the creation of many diverse

languages according to the community that creates the language itself (Budhianto, 2018).

In the process of implementing Arabic learning, it is necessary to pay attention to the emotional intelligence approach of students. This needs to be considered considering that emotional intelligence can affect the learning interactions that occur, class management, level of focus so that it can increase the excitement of students. One of the success factors for learning is how the classroom management is carried out and how the teaching process itself is. Classroom management is a skill possessed by teachers in maintaining and creating good teaching and learning situations and if there are obstacles in the learning process, the teacher can rearrange them (Manzilah et al., 2019).

Psychologically, classroom management is a process that creates a learning climate that emotionally and socially creates a positive relationship between teachers and students. In other words, this class management is the beginning of the success or failure of the learning process carried out. Classroom management that involves emotional intelligence can minimize the occurrence of problems in the learning process. In addition, students consciously can more easily grow self-confidence so that they can find out their potential. This good self-management allows students to regulate disturbing emotions and impulses so that they do not damage the learning atmosphere and can more easily adapt to the environment. Learning that relates to emotional intelligence must be able to be practiced in everyday life, so it doesn't just stop at theory. It is hoped that the repetition of learning habits using an emotional approach can later turn into characters and habits (Maulana et al., 2020).

Currently, the world, not only in Indonesia, is struggling against a pandemic that has had a major impact on all fields, including the world of education. Currently, learning cannot be done face-to-face so online learning must be ready to be carried out. There are many consequences that must be accepted by students in participating in online learning such as difficulties in understanding lessons to experience stress (Sadikin & Hamidah, 2020). Based on a survey by the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) conducted on students and teachers on April 13-21, 2020, it was found that 79.9% of students said that online learning had been done without interaction. In this context, students continue that the teacher only gives and collects assignments without learning interactions such as explaining learning material or asking questions. This large number triggers some students to experience fatigue. The remaining 20.1 percent of students stated that there was a learning interaction in the classroom.

This phenomenon that occurs interprets that in participating in online learning (online) students are expected to be able to motivate themselves through good self-regulation in doing assignments and being responsible for learning hours at home. Due to the limited control of teachers in online learning, only a few students are able to accept and understand this learning (Puteri & Dewi, 2020). Students who are able to accept and understand this are students who have high learning motivation and can manage study time

well. The obstacles that occur are not only limited to teacher and parental controls but also to adequate facilities and infrastructure such as ownership of smartphones, laptops, and the lack of an existing internet network (Handarini & Wulandari, 2020).

This shows that emotional intelligence has an important role in online learning. Emotional intelligence in this learning will make students have personal skills such as being responsible, able to control themselves, high learning motivation, and have self-awareness as students. This self-regulation has a big impact on controlling emotions so that students are not easily stressed. With good motivation, students will be encouraged to look for additional material and increase independent activities at home so that the material presented by the teacher is easier to understand.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be seen that the emotional intelligence approach is intelligence that includes how a person controls himself, motivates himself to self-awareness to be responsible for his work. In its development, if this emotional intelligence approach is applied in learning Arabic, it will have a good influence on students considering that teaching and learning activities are currently carried out online (online). This good influence includes students will have self-skills such as being motivated in learning, students will be able to control emotions, have self-control so they are not easily stressed in learning. In other words, the emotional intelligence approach is expected to have a positive and significant impact on online learning of Arabic in Indonesia.

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